

Magnetic, Magnetocaloric and Electric Transport Properties of Sr₂FeMoO_{6-δ} Double Perovskites with Different Degrees of Superstructural Ordering

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Abstract

Pressed strontium ferromolybdate (Sr₂FeMoO_{6-δ}) pellets with different oxygen indices δ and degrees of superstructural ordering were synthesized by solid-phase and citrate-gel methods to study magnetic and electric transport behaviors of this compound. The crystalline structure of the samples was found to demonstrate ordering of the Fe and Mo cations, which increases with increase of δ . The saturation magnetization and the Curie temperature of the samples correlate with the degree of superstructural ordering. The Banerjee criterion indicates that the compounds studied undergo a second order phase transition. The temperature dependence of the isothermal change of entropy in magnetic field was determined by the Maxwell approach. The additional low-temperature annealing was found to change the sample conductivity of metallic type for semiconducting one and significantly increases magnetoresistance due to the intergrain electron tunneling.

Keywords: strontium ferromolybdate, double perovskites, superstructural ordering, magnetocaloric effect, magnetoresistance

1. Introduction

$\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ (strontium ferromolybdate or SFMO) is a novel double perovskite half-metallic ferrimagnet^[1,2] combining such benefits as large low-field magnetoresistance^[3], high Curie temperature T_c , excellent phase stability and high electric conductivity. These properties make this material desirable for spintronic and solid oxide fuel cell applications.^[4-7] The different routes including sol-gel method,^[8] solid state reaction,^[9] microwave sintering^[10] etc. are employed to fabricate SFMO samples with improved characteristics including high spin polarization, magnetization, Curie temperature and defects free structure.

In order to achieve higher degree of the spin polarization in the strontium ferromolybdate, a occurrence of the superstructural ordering (SO) of Fe/Mo cations is required. Ideally, the Fe/Mo cations are integrated in two interleaving fcc sublattices as centers of FeO_6 and MoO_6 octahedra. This structure undergoes octahedral tilting transition,^[11] at which FeO_6 and MoO_6 are rotating around the crystallographic axis c .

High temperature $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ phase has the cubic structure $\text{Fm}\bar{3}\text{m}$ ($Z=2$) with the lattice parameter $c \approx 7.8 \text{ \AA}$. The ferrimagnetic order is observed in the tetragonal structure belonging to the spatial group of I4/m ($Z=2$) with the lattice parameters of $(c/\sqrt{2}, c/\sqrt{2}, c)$ at $T < T_c$. This is formed by the ordering of Fe and Mo electron spins in non-collinear configuration consisting of the planes, intersecting at an angle of 120° .^[12] A presence of the antisite defects $[\text{Fe}_{\text{Mo}}]$ and $[\text{Mo}_{\text{Fe}}]$ destroys SO, making a significant influence on the magnetic structure of the strontium ferromolybdate.^[12-13] On the plus side, modification of SO degree through formation of oxygen vacancies into $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ allows to tune certain parameters of magnetic system, as will be shown in this work.

The most valuable features generating practical interest to this compound are its Curie temperature higher than in perovskites and 100% electron spin polarization^[3] at the Fermi level. High Curie temperature together with large magnetization are prerequisites for practical application of magnetocaloric effect while the high spin polarization of carriers enhances magnetoresistance. Herein, the we estimate magnetocaloric effect (MCE) and consider evolution of magnetoresistance as $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ resistivity varies from metallic to semiconducting type through intermediate one.

The maximum magnitude of MCE is expected in the vicinity of phase transformations and can be determined by magnetic or calorimetric methods. But indirect Maxwell approach based on magnetization measurements fails in case of the first order phase transitions (FOPT).^[14] The magnetic structure during FOPT is inhomogeneous and the Maxwell relation does not take into account a change of the lattice entropy, which also makes contribution into MCE. The structural and the Curie transitions in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ coincide or occur very close to each other.

Employment of Maxwell relation can only be justified if this coupled magnetostructural transition is a second order one or a weakly FOPT. There is no information in literature about impact of SO in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ on an order of phase transition therefore this should be established prior to the estimation of magnetocaloric effect

2. Experimental

The $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ polycrystalline samples were synthesized by the solid-phase technique from $\text{SrFeO}_{2.52}$ and SrMoO_4 precursors. The precursors were obtained from MoO_3 , Fe_2O_3 and SrCO_3 compounds using standard ceramic technology. Grinding and agitation of the initial reagents have been carried out by vibromill in alcohol for 3 h. The obtained mixtures were dried at $T=570$ K. Initial annealing has been performed in air at 970 and 1070 K for 20 h and 40 h, respectively. A secondary agitation was used to increase the batch homogeneity. The final synthesis of the SrFeO_{3-x} compound was performed at $T = 1470$ K for 20 h in Ar flow, while the SrMoO_4 compound has been prepared at $T = 1470$ K for 40 h under $p(\text{O}_2) = 0.21 \cdot 10^5$ Pa with a subsequent annealing at room temperature, which was followed by room temperature tempering. The oxygen content in SrFeO_{3-x} has been determined by weighing before and after its complete reduction into a simple oxide SrO and Fe in hydrogen flow at 1373 K for 20 h. It was determined that the strontium ferrite had a composition $\text{SrFeO}_{2.52}$. The $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ was synthesized in the form of pellets with diameter of 10 mm and thickness of 4–5 mm, which have been pressed from the initial reagents $\text{SrFeO}_{2.52}$ and SrMoO_4 mixed in the stoichiometric ratio. Annealing of the pellets was carried out in the 5% H_2/Ar gas mixture at 1420 K for 5 h with a subsequent tempering at room temperature. The oxygen content in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ has been determined by weighing before and after its complete reduction into SrO, Fe and Mo in hydrogen flow at 1373 K for 20 h.

The study of electric transport properties was conducted on the specimens obtained from powders, which were synthesized by citrate-gel method. The details of their preparation can be found elsewhere.^[15] After the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ specimens had been compacted under pressure of 4 GPa at $T=800$ K, two of them were subjected to additional annealing at $T=700$ K for 3 and 5 hours. The phase composition has been determined from XRD data by the Rietveld technique using the ICSD–PDF2 (Release 2000) database and PowderCell, FullProf software. The XRD patterns were measured at room temperature at a rate of 60° per hour in the angular range of 10° – 90° using the Philips X' Pert MPD diffractometer with Cu-K_α radiation. The degree of SO

(P) of iron and molybdenum cations has been calculated using the expression $P = (1 - 2 \cdot AO) \cdot 100\%$, where AO is the anti-site occupancy. AO was determined by the Rietveld method using the POWDERCELL and FullProf software. The DC resistivity and magnetoresistance have been measured by the four terminal method. The magnetic field was applied along the current direction. The magnetic properties were studied by the ponderomotive and vibrating sample magnetometry in the temperature range 77–800 K.

3. Results and Discussion

The XRD data have shown that the initial pressed strontium ferromolybdate samples synthesized by the solid-phase technique had a single-phase composition without SO of iron and molybdenum cations ($P=56\%$). In order to obtain various δ and P parameters the initial samples were annealed at 1420 K in the stream of 5% H₂/Ar gas mixture for 15 h (sample SF-1, Sr₂FeMoO_{5.97}, $P = 76\%$), 50 h (SF-2, Sr₂FeMoO_{5.94}, $P = 86\%$) and 90 h (SF-3, Sr₂FeMoO_{5.94}, $P = 93\%$).

The oxygen index δ and P demonstrated saturation after certain time of annealing. Their saturation values appeared proportional to the temperature of annealing. The saturation value of δ was growing with temperature up to the highest temperature of 1470 K whereas that of the SO degree was peaked at 1420 K. At 1420 K, δ and P reached the saturation after annealing for 20 and 70 hours, respectively. In contrast, the drop of the SO degree and no saturation of δ and P with growth of annealing time are reported in works^[16,17] at 1430 K. These discrepancies are caused by high sensitivity of Sr₂FeMoO_{6.8} to synthesis conditions and entails poor reproducibility of its magnetic and transport properties.^[3,18]

Temperature dependences of the magnetization $M(T)$ at 0.86 T are given in **Figure 1**. A sharp decrease of the magnetization with temperature is observed in the region of the Curie point T_C . The presence of the (101) and (103) reflections indicates a formation of SO of iron and molybdenum (Fe/Mo) cations in the strontium ferromolybdate (the inset in **Figure 1**). As is seen, (101) and (103) reflections demonstrate growth of intensity with an increase of the P parameter. The magnetization also increases with P in the range of 77-550 K, and at 77 K, $M(\text{SF-1})_{77\text{K}} = 26.41 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, $M(\text{SF-2})_{77\text{K}} = 32.36 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ and $M(\text{SF-3})_{77\text{K}} = 42.66 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ (**Figure 1**). The Curie temperatures were determined as the temperature points where lines tangent to the magnetization curves at the maximum slope dM/dT intersect temperature axis.

The samples were found to have different Curie temperatures: $T_C \approx 422$ K, $T_C \approx 428$ K and $T_C \approx 437$ K for SF-1, SF-2 and SF-3, respectively. The magnetization values are practically equal to zero in the paramagnetic state.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of the SF-1, SF-2 and SF-3 magnetizations measured in magnetic field $\mu_0H=0.86$ T. Inset: the XRD patterns of SF-1, SF-2 and SF-3.

These findings indicate that SO increases the Curie temperature and the magnetization of the samples, which is consistent with the results of Monte Carlo simulation.^[19]

Electron hopping interaction, which causes $\text{Fe}(t_{2g})\text{-O}(2p)\text{-Mo}(t_{2g})$ hybridization in SFMO, stabilizes ferromagnetic arrangement of localized Fe spins. Thus, when SO is impaired and Mo atom replaces Fe one and vice versa, electron hopping and, respectively, double exchange mechanism can not be realized. This results in weakening ferromagnetic coupling in SFMO samples and decreasing Curie temperature and magnetization. Moreover, in this case, Kramers-Anderson model of superexchange interaction predicts occurrence of antiferromagnetic coupling between Fe cation in its own position and Fe cations occupying the nearest Mo positions. This coupling is responsible for appearance of antiferromagnetic clusters, which were observed in SANS measurements.^[20]

Another exchange mechanism that can be realized in double perovskites assumes itinerant electron spin contribution into total magnetic moment. In the framework of the model^[21] incorporating this assumption, T_C is proportional to density of states at the Fermi level^[22]. Decreasing Curie temperature and magnetization as the degree of SO is reducing follows from this model as well, since the first principle calculations^[23,24] have shown that the antisite disorder leads to appearance of new states in the majority spin band at the Fermi level. Thus, the electrons from these states

have spins opposite to total magnetic moment of the minority spins that deteriorates magnetic properties.

It should be noted that oxygen nonstoichiometry does not have significant influence on magnetic properties of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ samples studied here since the SF-2, SF-3 samples with identical δ demonstrate different T_c and magnetization.

The change of isothermal magnetization curves with temperature and their shape are almost identical for all compositions studied and the only difference is the saturation magnetization value, which increases with P for the specific temperature. The magnetization curves obtained for the SF-3 sample reflect change of its magnetic behavior in the temperature range of 366-428 K (**Figure 2**). As temperature approaches the Curie temperature, the variation of magnetization with field acquires linear character inherent in paramagnetic phase.

Figure 2. Isothermal magnetization curves of SF-3 sample.

It was noted above that the magnetic transition in the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ double perovskite is accompanied by structural tilting transition leading to the distortion of the unit cell. The order of this transition is difficult to identify from magnetization curves. But this can be done using the Arrott $H/M(M^2)$ plots, which describe critical phenomena in the vicinity of the phase transition according to the mean field approximation. In line with Banerjee criterion,^[25] a negative slope $d(H/M)/d(M^2)$ corresponds to FOPT, while a positive slope corresponds to a second order magnetic phase transition. As it follows from **Figure 3**, all curves have a positive slope. Thus, phase transitions at $T=T_C$ in the samples with different P and δ are second order ones.

Figure 3. The Arrott plots for (a) SF-1 sample, (b) SF-2 sample and (c) SF-3 sample.

MCE in the SF-3 sample was studied by the Maxwell method using isothermal magnetization curves (**Figure 2**). As it was already mentioned in the Introduction section this method is applicable to continuous second order phase transitions, which were confirmed to occur in the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ studied here. The essence of this method lies in using the equation derived from the Maxwell relation. In case of discrete isothermal magnetization curves, the change of entropy due to MCE can be approximately expressed by $\Delta S(T, H) = \int_0^H \left(\frac{\partial M(T, H)}{\partial T} \right)_H dH$. Using the numerical procedure, the temperature dependence of MCE in the SF-3 sample can be given as $|\Delta S_M| = \sum_i \frac{M_i - M_{i+1}}{T_{i+1} - T_i} \Delta H$. As it follows from **Figure 4** the maximum of ΔS is observed at the temperature of the highest dM/dT slope in accordance with the Maxwell relation. Increasing temperature of measurements results in smooth decreasing MCE, while the compound transforms into nonmagnetic state. The temperature range, wherein the adiabatic entropy change exceeds 0,5 J/kg·K, extends from 370 to 420 K.

Figure 4. The temperature dependent change of entropy in SF-3 sample under different magnetic fields.

The maximum magnitude of MCE in the field of 10 kOe is much larger than early reported values for $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ ^[26, 27] and reaches the magnitude characteristic of rare-earth magnetic materials such as Gd, Tb^[28] that makes strontium ferromolybdate prospective for magnetic refrigeration. The comparison of the results presented here with those from previous works^[26, 27, 29] reveals higher values of M , dM/dT and T_C for the SF-3 sample. Considering the correlation between the degree of SO and values of M and T_C obtained in this study, one can suppose that high SO degree is responsible for enhancing MCE in the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$.

It is well known that employment of different synthesis and annealing methods allows to vary conductivity of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ in a wide range. One of the routes of tuning transport properties is an additional low-temperature annealing in Ar/O₂ flow. This process favours oxidation and leads to a build-up of the SrMoO_4 dielectric intergrain layers due to the transition of molybdenum cations Mo^{5+} on the grain surface into different valence state Mo^{6+} thus radically changing the conduction mechanisms. Appearance of the SrMoO_4 reflections in XRD pattern and absence of any magnetization change after annealing (not shown here) indicate that oxidation does not affect the bulk of the grain and occurs mainly between the grains.

The effect of low-temperature annealing on the resistivity of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ is clearly seen in **Figure 5**. The resistivities of the not-annealed sample A, the samples B and C after annealing at 700 K for 3 and 5 hours, respectively, display different temperature dependent behavior. They increase with the annealing time and amount to $\rho=0,537 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$, $\rho=0,696 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$, $\rho=579431 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ for the A, B and C samples at 300 K. The resistivity magnitudes of the samples A and B are characteristic of polycrystalline half-metals, while the resistivity of the sample C is in the range characteristic of semiconductors. It is in line with temperature dependences, which demonstrate metallic type of conduction with $d\rho/dT > 0$ for the sample A (**Figure 5, a**), $d\rho/dT < 0$ at low and $d\rho/dT > 0$ at higher

temperatures for the sample B (**Figure 5, b**), $d\rho/dT < 0$ for the sample C (**Figure 5, c**). In the former case, $\rho(T)$ is proportional to T^2 ,^[30,31] which implies scattering by magnons or by electrons as dominant electron scattering mechanism. The conduction electrons in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ are 4d electrons from Mo (t_{2g}) sub-band with weak electron-electron correlations.^[32] Thus, electron-magnon scattering is mainly responsible for temperature behavior of electrical resistivity in case of metallic $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$. Earlier, a similar $\rho(T^2)$ behavior was reported in single crystal SFMO.^[33]

Figure 5. Resistivities as functions of temperature in different magnetic fields for (a) the not-annealed sample A, (b) the sample B annealed at 700 K for 3 hours and (c) the sample C annealed at 700 K for 3 hours.

As for the sample C demonstrating semiconducting behavior, the best fits were achieved with $\ln(\rho/\rho_0) \propto T^{-1/4}$ (Mott variable-range hopping model) and $\ln(\rho/\rho_0) \propto T^{-1/2}$ (Efros-Shklovski variable-range hopping model).^[34] Applicability of both models implies that charge current in semiconducting SFMO is realized by electron hopping mechanism, which provides electron tunneling through localized states in dielectric SrMoO_4 intergrain barriers.

Application of magnetic field has almost no effect on the temperature behavior of all the sample resistivities except for increase of temperature whereby the temperature coefficient of resistivity

changes its sign (**Figure 5, b**). The far larger values of resistivity of the sample C compared to A and B are accounted for by the formation of the dielectric SrMoO₄ layers separating grains during the additional annealing.

As it follows from **Figure 5**, the magnetoresistance ($MR(\%)=100\% \cdot (R(H,T)-R(0,T))/R(0,T)$) of all the samples studied is negative and its magnitude reduces with temperature. The magnitude of MR of the sample C is remarkably larger than that of metallic A and B samples. The maximal values of MR were 21.2% for the sample A, 26.1% for the sample B and 43,6 % for the sample C at $T=10$ K and $\mu_0H=10$ T.

The scattering mechanisms lying behind magnetoresistance are different in the samples A and C. In the former case, SFMO is a metallic compound composed of nanocrystalline grains, which are electrically connected each other. As such, this system is similar to a common metallic ferrimagnet with magnetic moments localized on the cations Fe³⁺ and Mo⁵⁺. Since Sr₂FeMoO_{6-δ} possesses high spin polarization^[3], change of spin dependent scattering of electrons on the localized moments in magnetic field yields higher magnitude of magnetoresistance than, for example, in routine 3d ferromagnets with lower spin polarization.

Each grain in the sample C is embedded in dielectric shell so that no direct contact between conducting bulks of adjacent grains is possible. In such a system, only tunneling intergrain magnetoresistance is realized. Probability of electron tunnelling increases if magnetic moments of adjacent grains are parallel. Thus, application of magnetic field increases probability of electron transfer through potential barrier of dielectric intergrain layer and causes drop of resistivity. The intergrain tunneling magnetoresistance can be described in the framework of the simple model^[35] by the relationship:

$$MR = \frac{P^2 \left(\frac{M}{M_S}\right)^2}{1 + P^2 \left(\frac{M}{M_S}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where M_S is the saturation magnetization, P is the spin polarization. Decreasing magnetoresistance magnitude with temperature seen in **Figure 5, c** complies with this relationship since P and M/M_S also reduce with temperature.

From equation (1), one can estimate the spin polarization of the sample C. Assuming $M/M_S=1$, one have $P = \left(\frac{MR_{sat}}{1 - MR_{sat}} \right)^{1/2}$ where MR_{sat} is the magnetoresistance corresponding to the magnetic saturation field. Substituting $MR_{sat} = 0.44$ in the last expression, one obtains $P=89\%$ for the sample C at 100 K.

The field dependence of the magnetoresistance of the sample C constitutes the butterfly-shaped curves below the Curie temperature approaching to the saturation in high fields (**Figure 6, a**). The

steepest growth of the magnetoresistance as well as the magnetization (**Figure 6, b**) occur in low fields (<0.3 T). The correlation between these parameters can be expressed as $MR \propto (M/M_s)^2$ that is clearly seen especially in the fields far below the saturation ones.

Figure 6. Magnetoresistance and the square of normalized magnetization of the sample C as functions of magnetic field at 100 K.

This scaling law can be easily derived from (1) on the premise that P and $M/M_s < 1$. The same scaling was observed in other double perovskite systems including semiconducting $\text{La}_2\text{NiMnO}_6$,^[36] and metallic $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$.^[37] In spite of the lack of tunneling mechanism, $MR \propto (M/M_s)^2$ is also characteristic of GMR in granular alloys^[38] since the spin dependent scattering depends on relative orientation of grain magnetic moments in that case as well.

4. Conclusions

- $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ samples prepared by the solid phase method with various oxygen indexes δ and the degrees of superstructural ordering P exhibit phase transitions of a second order with close characteristic (Curie) temperatures; the sample with higher degree of SO possesses higher magnetization and the Curie temperature.

- The isothermal change of entropy of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{5.94}$ with $P=93\%$ reaches $1\text{ J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$ under magnetic field of 10 kOe that makes this compound attractive for magnetocaloric applications.
- The additional annealing of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ samples prepared by citrate-gel method in Ar/O_2 flow at 700 K for 5 hours changes the conduction mechanism from metallic type to semiconducting one.
- The sample after the additional annealing demonstrates enhancing magnetoresistance from 21.2% to 43.6% due to the intergrain tunneling through dielectric SrMoO_4 layers.

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